

Pre Separation Axioms In Neutrosophic Crisp Topological Spaces

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Abstract

In this paper, A new type of separation axioms in the neutrosophic crisp Topological space named neutrosophic crisp pre separation axioms is going to be defined , in which neutrosophic crisp pre open set and neutrosophic crisp point are to be depended on. Also, relations among them and the other type are going to be found.

Keywords: Neutrosophic crisp pre separation axiom, neutrosophic crisp separation axiom, neutrosophic crisp point, Neutrosophic crisp semi separation axiom.

1. Introduction

In 1995, F.Samarandache generalized the fuzzy logic concept into the neutrosophic logic which presents a more detaied and concise description than the fuzzy logic and classical logic; then several researches emerged in this logic, in all branches of mathematics, especially Topology.

In 2012 A. A Salama et al. defined the concept of the neutrosophic set. Also, in 2020 A. Al-Nafey, R. Al-Hamido and F. Smarandache define the neutrosophic crisp separation axioms[2]. Also, in 2020 R. K. Al-Hamido, L.A. Salha and T. Gharibah define neutrosophic crisp semi separation axioms[13].

Recently, the neutrosophic crisp set theory may have applications in image processing [3-4]and possible applications to database[6]. Also, neutrosophic sets [7] have applications in the medical field [8-11], [9], [10], [11] and in the field of geographic information systems[5].Many researchers studied topology, and they had many contributions to neutrosophic topology as [14], [15], [16], [17] and [18] and in neutrosophic bitopology in [19], [20], [21] and [22], and in neutrosophic algebra in [23], [24], [25], [26] and [27].

In this paper, neutrosophic crisp pre separation axioms via neutrosophic crisp pre open set and neutrosophic crisp point are going to be studied.

Lastly, the definition of separation axioms is as follows $T_i, i = 0,1,2$ and the relations among them.

2. Preliminaries

In this paper, the symbol (χ, T) means a neutrosophic crisp topological space (N_cTS), Also

$N_c.OS$ ($N_c.CS$) means a neutrosophic crisp open(closed) sets and neutrosophic crisp pre open set in N_cTS mean a $N_cP.OS$.

Some important definitions to this paper will be shown.

Definition 2.1. [1]

Suppos that $X \neq \emptyset$ be a fixed set. A neutrosophic crisp set ($N_c.S$) U is an object with the $U = \langle U_1, U_2, U_3 \rangle$ shape; U_1, U_2 and U_3 are subsets of X .

Definition 2.5. [12]

Suppos that χ be a non-empty set. And $x, y, z \in \chi$, then:

- $x_{N_1} = \langle \{x\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$ is called a neutrosophic crisp point ($N_cP_{N_1}$) in χ .
- $y_{N_2} = \langle \emptyset, \{y\}, \emptyset \rangle$ is called a neutrosophic crisp point ($N_cP_{N_2}$) in χ .
- $z_{N_3} = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{z\} \rangle$ is called a neutrosophic crisp point ($N_cP_{N_3}$) in χ .

The set of all neutrosophic crisp points ($N_cP_{N_1}, N_cP_{N_2}, N_cP_{N_3}$) is denoted by NCP_N .

Definition 2.6. [12]

Suppos that (χ, T) be an $NcTS$. Then χ is called:

- N_1T_0 -space for every two diffrant points from χ there exists neutrosophic crisp open set in χ containing one of them but not the other.
- N_2T_0 -space for every two diffrant points from χ there exists neutrosophic crisp open set in χ containing one of them but not the other.
- N_3T_0 -space for every two diffrant points from χ there exists neutrosophic crisp open set in χ containing one of them but not the other.

Definition 2.7. [12]

Suppos that (χ, T) be an $NcTS$. Then χ is called:

- N_1T_1 -space for every two diffrant points from χ are x_{N_1}, y_{N_1} there exists two neutrosophic crisp open set M_1, M_2 in χ such that $x_{N_1} \in M_1, y_{N_1} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin M_2, y_{N_1} \in M_2$.
- N_2T_1 -space for every two diffrant points from χ are x_{N_1}, y_{N_1} there exists two neutrosophic crisp open set M_1, M_2 in χ such that $x_{N_2} \in G_1, y_{N_2} \notin G_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin G_2, y_{N_2} \in G_2$.
- N_3T_1 -space for every two diffrant points from χ are x_{N_1}, y_{N_1} there exists two neutrosophic crisp open set M_1, M_2 in χ such that $x_{N_3} \in M_1, y_{N_3} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin M_2, y_{N_3} \in M_2$.

Definition 2.8. [12]

Suppos that (χ, T) be an $NcTS$. Then χ is called:

- N_1T_2 -space for every two diffrant points from χ are x_{N_1}, y_{N_1} there exists two neutrosophic crisp open set M_1, M_2 in χ such that $x_{N_1} \in M_1, y_{N_1} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin M_2, y_{N_1} \in M_2$. with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$.
- N_2T_2 -space for every two diffrant points from χ are x_{N_1}, y_{N_1} there exists two neutrosophic crisp open set M_1, M_2 in χ such that $x_{N_2} \in M_1, y_{N_2} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin M_2, y_{N_2} \in M_2$ with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$.
- N_3T_2 -space for every two diffrant points from χ are x_{N_1}, y_{N_1} there exists two neutrosophic crisp open set M_1, M_2 in χ such that $x_{N_3} \in M_1, y_{N_3} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin M_2, y_{N_3} \in M_2$ with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$.

Definition 2.9. [13]

Suppos that (χ, T) be an $NcTS$. Then χ is called:

- N_1 semi T_0 -space if for every $x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1} \in \chi$ there exists $NcS.OS$ M in χ containing one of them but not the other.
- N_2 semi T_0 -space if $\forall x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2} \in \chi$ there exists $NcS.OS$ M in χ containing one of them but not the other.
- N_3 semi T_0 -space if $\forall x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3} \in \chi$ there exists $NcS.OS$ M in χ containing one of them but not the other.

Definition 2.10. [13]

Suppos that $(\chi, \mathcal{T})$ be an $NcTS$. Then χ is called:

- a. N_1 semi $\mathcal{T}_1$ -space if for every $x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1} \in \chi$ there exist $NcS.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_1} \in M_1, y_{N_1} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin M_2, y_{N_1} \in M_2$.
- b. N_2 semi $\mathcal{T}_1$ -space if $\forall x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2} \in \chi$ there exist $NcS.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_2} \in G_1, y_{N_2} \notin G_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin G_2, y_{N_2} \in G_2$.
- c. N_3 semi $\mathcal{T}_1$ -space if $\forall x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3} \in \chi$ there exist $NcS.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_3} \in M_1, y_{N_3} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin M_2, y_{N_3} \in M_2$.

Definition 2.11. [13]

Suppos that $(\chi, \mathcal{T})$ be an $NcTS$. Then χ is called:

- a. N_1 semi $\mathcal{T}_2$ -space if for every $x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1} \in \chi$ there exists $NcS.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_1} \in M_1, y_{N_1} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin M_2, y_{N_1} \in M_2$. with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$.
- b. N_2 semi $\mathcal{T}_2$ -space if $\forall x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2} \in \chi$ there exists $NcS.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_2} \in M_1, y_{N_2} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin M_2, y_{N_2} \in M_2$ with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$.
- c. N_3 semi $\mathcal{T}_2$ -space if $\forall x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3} \in \chi$ there exists $NcS.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_3} \in M_1, y_{N_3} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin M_2, y_{N_3} \in M_2$ with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$.

3. Separation axioms via pre open sets

This section introuduces a new type of separation axioms in the neutrosophic crisp Topological space named neutrosophic crisp pre separation axioms.

Definition 3.1.

Suppos that $(\chi, \mathcal{T})$ be an $NcTS$. Then χ is called:

- d. N_1 pre $\mathcal{T}_0$ -space if for every $x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1} \in \chi$ there exists $NcP.OS M$ in χ containing one of them but not the other.
- e. N_2 pre $\mathcal{T}_0$ -space if $\forall x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2} \in \chi$ there exists $NcP.OS M$ in χ containing one of them but not the other.
- f. N_3 pre $\mathcal{T}_0$ -space if $\forall x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3} \in \chi$ there exists $NcP.OS M$ in χ containing one of them but not the other.

Definition 3.2.

Suppos that $(\chi, \mathcal{T})$ be an $NcTS$. Then χ is called:

- d. N_1 $\mathcal{T}_1$ -space if for every $x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1} \in \chi$ there exist $NcP.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_1} \in M_1, y_{N_1} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin M_2, y_{N_1} \in M_2$.
- e. N_2 pre $\mathcal{T}_1$ -space if $\forall x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2} \in \chi$ there exist $NcP.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_2} \in G_1, y_{N_2} \notin G_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin G_2, y_{N_2} \in G_2$.
- f. N_3 pre $\mathcal{T}_1$ -space if $\forall x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3} \in \chi$ there exist $NcP.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_3} \in M_1, y_{N_3} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin M_2, y_{N_3} \in M_2$.

Definition 3.3.

Suppos that $(\chi, \mathcal{T})$ be an $NcTS$. Then χ is called:

- d. N_1 pre $\mathcal{T}_2$ -space if for every $x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1} \in \chi$ there exists $NcP.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_1} \in M_1, y_{N_1} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin M_2, y_{N_1} \in M_2$. with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$.
- e. N_2 pre $\mathcal{T}_2$ -space if $\forall x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2} \in \chi$ there exists $NcP.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_2} \in M_1, y_{N_2} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin M_2, y_{N_2} \in M_2$ with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$.
- f. N_3 pre $\mathcal{T}_2$ -space if $\forall x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3} \in \chi$ there exists $NcP.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_3} \in M_1, y_{N_3} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin M_2, y_{N_3} \in M_2$ with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$.

Theorem 3.4.

Suppos that $(\chi, \mathcal{T})$ be an $NcTS$, then :

1. Every $N_1 \mathcal{T}_0$ -space is N_1 pre $\mathcal{T}_0$ -space.
2. Every $N_2 \mathcal{T}_0$ -space is N_2 pre $\mathcal{T}_0$ -space.
3. Every $N_3 \mathcal{T}_0$ -space is N_3 pre $\mathcal{T}_0$ -space.

Proof:

1. Suppose that $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ is an $N_1\mathbb{T}_0$ -space, therefore for every two $x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1}$, there exists an N_c -OS M in χ containing one of them to which the other does not belong. So there exists an NcP -OS M in χ containing one of them to which the other does not belong, therefore X is $N_1pre\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.
2. Suppose that $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ is an $N_2\mathbb{T}_0$ -space, therefore for every two $x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2}$, there exists an N_c -OS M in χ containing one of them to which the other does not belong. So there exists an NcP -OS M in χ containing one of them to which the other does not belong, therefore X is $N_2pre\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.
3. Suppose that $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ is an $N_3\mathbb{T}_0$ -space, therefore for every two $x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3}$, there exists an N_c -OS M in χ containing one of them to which the other does not belong. So there exists an NcP -OS M in χ containing one of them to which the other does not belong, therefore X is $N_3pre\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.

Remark 3.5.

The converse of theorem 3.4 is not true, as it is shown in the following examples.

Example 3.6.

Let $\chi = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathbb{T} = \{\emptyset_N, X_N, A\}$, $A = \{\langle \{a\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}$

NcP -OS = $\mathbb{T} \cup \{B = \{\langle \{a, c\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}, C = \{\langle \{a, b\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}\}$.

Let $x_{N_1} = \{\langle \{b\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\} \neq y_{N_1} = \{\langle \{c\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is no a N_c -OS M in χ containing one of them but not the other. Therefore $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ is not $N_1\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.

Let $x_{N_1} = \{\langle \{b\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\} \neq y_{N_1} = \{\langle \{a\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is a NcP -OS B in χ containing one of them but not the other.

Let $x_{N_1} = \{\langle \{a\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\} \neq y_{N_1} = \{\langle \{c\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is a NcP -OS A in χ containing one of them but not the other.

Let $x_{N_1} = \{\langle \{b\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\} \neq y_{N_1} = \{\langle \{c\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is a N_c -OS B in χ containing one of them but not the other. Therefore $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ $N_1pre\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.

Then $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ $N_1pre\mathbb{T}_0$ -space, But $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ is not $N_1\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.

Example 3.7.

Let $\chi = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathbb{T} = \{\emptyset_N, X_N, A\}$, $A = \{\langle \{a\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}$

NcP -OS = $\mathbb{T} \cup \{B = \{\langle \{a, c\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}, C = \{\langle \{a, b\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}\}$.

Let $x_{N_2} = \{\langle \emptyset, \{b\}, \emptyset \rangle\} \neq y_{N_2} = \{\langle \emptyset, \{c\}, \emptyset \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is no a N_c -OS M in χ containing one of them but not the other. Therefore $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ is not $N_2\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.

Let $x_{N_2} = \{\langle \emptyset, \{b\}, \emptyset \rangle\} \neq y_{N_2} = \{\langle \emptyset, \{c\}, \emptyset \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is a NcP -OS B in χ containing one of them but not the other.

Let $x_{N_2} = \{\langle \emptyset, \{a\}, \emptyset \rangle\} \neq y_{N_2} = \{\langle \emptyset, \{c\}, \emptyset \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is a NcP -OS A in χ containing one of them but not the other.

Let $x_{N_2} = \{\langle \emptyset, \{b\}, \emptyset \rangle\} \neq y_{N_2} = \{\langle \emptyset, \{a\}, \emptyset \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is a NcP -OS A in χ containing one of them but not the other. Therefore $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ $N_2pre\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.

Then $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ $N_2pre\mathbb{T}_0$ -space, But $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ is not $N_2\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.

Example 3.8.

Let $\chi = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathbb{T} = \{\emptyset_N, X_N, A\}$, $A = \{\langle \{a\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}$

NcP -OS = $\mathbb{T} \cup \{B = \{\langle \{a, c\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}, C = \{\langle \{a, b\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}\}$.

Let $x_{N_3} = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{b\} \rangle\} \neq y_{N_3} = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{c\} \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is no a N_c -OS M in χ containing one of them but not the other. Therefore $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ is not $N_3\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.

Let $x_{N_3} = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{b\} \rangle\} \neq y_{N_3} = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{c\} \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is a NcP -OS B in χ containing one of them but not the other.

Let $x_{N_3} = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{a\} \rangle\} \neq y_{N_3} = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{c\} \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is a NcP -OS A in χ containing one of them but not the other.

Let $x_{N_3} = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{b\} \rangle\} \neq y_{N_3} = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{a\} \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is a N_c -OS A in χ containing one of them but not the other. Therefore $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ $N_3pre\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.

Then $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ $N_3pre\mathbb{T}_0$ -space, But $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ is not $N_3\mathbb{T}_0$ -space.

Theorem 3.9.

Let $(\chi, \mathbb{T})$ be an $N_c\mathbb{T}\mathbb{S}$, then :

1. Every $N_1\mathbb{T}_1$ -space is $N_1pre\mathbb{T}_1$ -space.

2. Every N_2T_1 -space is N_2preT_1 -space.
3. Every N_3T_1 -space is N_3preT_1 -space.

Proof:

1. Suppose that (χ, T) is an N_1T_1 -space, therefore for every two $x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1}$, there exist an $Nc.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_1} \in M_1, y_{N_1} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin M_2, y_{N_1} \in M_2$. So there exists an $NcP.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_1} \in M_1, y_{N_1} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin M_2, y_{N_1} \in M_2$.
Therefore X is N_1preT_1 -space.
2. Suppose that (χ, T) is an N_2T_1 -space, therefore for every two $x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2}$, there exist an $Nc.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_2} \in M_1, y_{N_2} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin M_2, y_{N_2} \in M_2$. So there exists an $NcP.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_2} \in M_1, y_{N_2} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin M_2, y_{N_2} \in M_2$.
Therefore X is N_2preT_1 -space.
3. Suppose that (χ, T) is an N_3T_1 -space, therefore for every two $x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3}$, there exist an $Nc.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_3} \in M_1, y_{N_3} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin M_2, y_{N_3} \in M_2$. So there exists an $NcP.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_3} \in M_1, y_{N_3} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin M_2, y_{N_3} \in M_2$.
Therefore X is N_3preT_1 -space.

Remark 3.10.

The converse of a theorem 3.9 is not true, as it is shown in the following example.

Example 3.11.

Let $\chi = \{a, b, c\}, T = \{\emptyset_N, X_N, A, B\}, A = \{\langle \{a\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}, B = \{\langle \{b, c\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}$.
 $NcP.OS = T \cup \{G = \{\langle \{b\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}, C = \{\langle \{c\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}, E = \{\langle \{a, b\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}, H = \{\langle \{a, c\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\}\}$.
 Let $x_{N_1} = \{\langle \{b\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\} \neq y_{N_1} = \{\langle \{c\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is no $Nc.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_1} \in M_1, y_{N_1} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin M_2, y_{N_1} \in M_2$. Therefore (χ, T) is not N_1T_1 -space.

Then $(\chi, T) N_1preT_1$ -space, but (χ, T) is not N_1T_1 -space.

Example 3.12.

Let $\chi = \{a, b, c\}, T = \{\emptyset_N, X_N, A, B\}, A = \{\langle \emptyset, \{a\}, \emptyset \rangle\}, B = \{\langle \emptyset, \{b, c\}, \emptyset \rangle\}$.
 $NcS.OS = T \cup \{G = \{\langle \emptyset, \{b\}, \emptyset \rangle\}, C = \{\langle \emptyset, \{c\}, \emptyset \rangle\}, E = \{\langle \emptyset, \{a, b\}, \emptyset \rangle\}, H = \{\langle \emptyset, \{a, c\}, \emptyset \rangle\}\}$.
 Let $x_{N_2} = \{\langle \emptyset, \{b\}, \emptyset \rangle\} \neq y_{N_2} = \{\langle \emptyset, \{c\}, \emptyset \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is no $Nc.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_2} \in M_1, y_{N_2} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin M_2, y_{N_2} \in M_2$. Therefore (χ, T) is not N_2T_1 -space.

Then $(\chi, T) N_2preT_1$ -space, but (χ, T) is not N_2T_1 -space.

Example 3.13.

Let $\chi = \{a, b, c\}, T = \{\emptyset_N, X_N, A, B\}, A = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{a\} \rangle\}, B = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{b, c\} \rangle\}$.
 $NcS.OS = T \cup \{G = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{b\} \rangle\}, C = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{c\} \rangle\}, E = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{a, b\} \rangle\}, H = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{a, c\} \rangle\}\}$.
 Let $x_{N_3} = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{b\} \rangle\} \neq y_{N_3} = \{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{c\} \rangle\} \in \chi$ there is no $Nc.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_3} \in M_1, y_{N_3} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin M_2, y_{N_3} \in M_2$. Therefore (χ, T) is not N_3T_1 -space.

Then $(\chi, T) N_3preT_1$ -space, but (χ, T) is not N_3T_1 -space.

Theorem 3.14.

Let (χ, T) be an $NcTS$, then :

1. Every N_1T_2 -space is N_1preT_2 -space.
2. Every N_2T_2 -space is N_2preT_2 -space.
3. Every N_3T_2 -space is N_3preT_2 -space.

Proof:

1. Suppose that (χ, T) is an N_1T_2 -space, therefore for every two $x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1}$, there exists an $Nc.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_1} \in M_1, y_{N_1} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin M_2, y_{N_1} \in M_2$. with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$. So there exists $NcP.OS M_1, M_2$ in χ such that $x_{N_1} \in M_1, y_{N_1} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin M_2, y_{N_1} \in M_2$. with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$.
Therefore X is N_1preT_2 -space.

2. Suppose that (χ, τ) is an N_2T_2 -space, therefore for every two $x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2}$, there exists an *Nc.OS* M_1, M_2 in χ such that $x_{N_2} \in M_1, y_{N_2} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin M_2, y_{N_2} \in M_2$. with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$. So there exists *NcP.OS* M_1, M_2 in χ such that $x_{N_2} \in M_1, y_{N_2} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin M_2, y_{N_2} \in M_2$. with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$. Therefore X is N_2preT_2 -space.
3. Suppose that (χ, τ) is an N_3T_2 -space, therefore for every two $x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3}$, there exists an *Nc.OS* M_1, M_2 in χ such that $x_{N_3} \in M_1, y_{N_3} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin M_2, y_{N_3} \in M_2$. with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$. So there exists *NcP.OS* M_1, M_2 in χ such that $x_{N_3} \in M_1, y_{N_3} \notin M_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin M_2, y_{N_3} \in M_2$. with $M_1 \cap M_2 = \emptyset$. Therefore X is N_3preT_2 -space.

4.

Remark 3.15.

The converse of the Theorem 3.14 is not true, as it is shown in the following example.

Example 3.16.

In example 3.11. (χ, τ) N_1preT_2 -space, but (χ, τ) is not N_1T_2 -space.

Example 3.17.

In example 3.12. (χ, τ) N_2preT_2 -space, but (χ, τ) is not N_2T_2 -space.

Example 3.18.

In example 3.13. (χ, τ) N_3preT_2 -space, but (χ, τ) is not N_3T_2 -space.

Theorem 3.19.

Let (χ, τ) be an N_cTS , then :

1. N_1preT_2 -space $\Rightarrow N_1preT_1$ -space $\Rightarrow N_1preT_0$ -space.
2. N_2preT_2 -space $\Rightarrow N_2preT_1$ -space $\Rightarrow N_2preT_0$ -space.
3. N_3preT_2 -space $\Rightarrow N_3preT_1$ -space $\Rightarrow N_3preT_0$ -space.

The converse of the Theorem 3.19 is not true.

Remark 3.21.

Relations among the different types of neutrosophic crisp separation axioms which were studied in this paper, appear in the following diagram.

Conclusion

In this paper, a new type of neutrosophic crisp separation axioms has been defined by using neutrosophic crisp pre open sets and certain point in the neutrosophic crisp topological spaces. Moreover, the connections between neutrosophic crisp pre separation axioms and the existing neutrosophic crisp separation axioms are studied. And many examples are presented to clear the concepts introduced. Also, proof their basic properties. Also, investigate their fundamental properties and characterizations.

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